

A ROOT – CAUSE ANALYSIS ON THE CHALLENGES OF NOVICE FACULTY MEMBERS IN TARLAC STATE UNIVERSITY

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ABSTRACT

The main functions of any instructor in any educational institution are to teach and be an effective education to their students, be an inspiration to their community and influence the university with great success. Upon transitioning to the new normal arrangement of teaching, most educators experience difficulties especially for those who are new in the field of teaching. Some literatures also state that having a good teaching evaluation rating proves no challenges in teaching. Hence, looking on the other side may reveal that every person that is new to the field experiences challenges in handling their loads in the teaching profession. The study used an exploratory research design. Specifically, the known as the Fishbone Diagram or Ishikawa Diagram along with a Root – Cause Analysis Quantitative Design. Total Sampling was employed since the study focuses on all faculty members hired during the pandemic era coming from different colleges. The study also used a qualitative approach specifically a phenomenological approach using Thematic analysis in identifying the challenges of faculty members and their motivational practices to continue their teaching profession. With all the methodological process, the study aims to identify the challenges in teaching experienced by the novice faculty members being hired during the new normal arrangement of teaching. The study identified three (3) categories of challenges of the faculty members, specifically, (a) class preparation, (b) class management and (c) instruction along with their personal and professional challenges. The study also revealed half of the Student Evaluation on Teaching has negative comments about the class preparation and instruction of the faculty members which reflects the difficulties experienced by the faculty members. Alongside, the faculty members also revealed that they have experienced challenges from both personal and professional aspects and are focus mostly on the

transitioning phase of different teaching strategies, professional growth, and skills development. The faculty members also shared their ways of coping with the challenges they have and with this, the study revealed that novice faculty members will always have these challenges with them but learning how to handle it will give them a positive SET afterwards.

Keywords: *root – cause, novice, evaluation, innovation, challenges*

INTRODUCTION

Newcomers are anticipated to acclimate to their roles promptly, familiarize themselves with tasks at their assigned workplaces, and establish rapport with management and colleagues. This represents a crucial phase in their lives, frequently marking the onset of a professional career. Transitioning to a new setting that lies beyond our comfort zones can induce stress for people embarking on a new job. Professional adaptation is the process of acclimating freshly hired personnel to the conditions of their work environment. This results from the process of acquiring new employees who have successfully undergone rigorous selection procedures. The effective adaptation of newly hired teaching personnel lacking prior expertise is likely to be a difficulty. This will enable them to become efficient and effective employees for the institution to which they applied. According to Salandanan in 2005, learning how to teach is never an easy task, especially if you do not have any foundation as some consider teaching to be a skill. Newly - hired teachers are faced with multiple challenges and become affected with multiple concerns and anxieties. Such feelings are expected but should not be a hindrance on their desire to "learn to teach" like how teachers who are newfound in the field experienced problems related to teaching and lesson preparation, including dealing with individual differences.

Furthermore, majority of the problems of teachers who are just starting were more about class management, lack of materials and time management (Basturk and Tastepe, 2015). Many educators reported problems in class and time management and evaluation of their own teaching effectiveness, while others experienced an unstable teaching environment because of political intervention (Richardson, 2014). Service – delivery issues, student characters, school climate, support systems, teacher preparation, paperwork requirements and consequent of efficacy of teachers during first year of service (Chakrabarty, 2016). This supports some claims that other non-teaching related tasks were given to faculty members despite being a newly – hired without prior training or mentoring.

Challenging experiences do not only have an impact on the moral principles and effectiveness of a newly – hired teaching personnel, but it can also affect the employees' attrition rate since most of them were forced to resign because of their difficulty adapting in the teaching profession. Even though training and seminars will be provided, the turnover rate will not decrease if the causes are not analyzed.

New faculty members of Tarlac State University with no prior teaching experiences encounter similar difficulties mentioned in literature. The teaching performance of faculty members affects the students' motivation to perform better in their board licensure examinations and in the professional field after graduation.

These student performances, in return, have an impact on the general performance in the university. Student evaluations of teaching (SET) is the most widely spread method to conduct teacher evaluation at institutions for higher education (Arnold, 2009). Different survey designs exist to conduct SET, but most often a SET survey instrument consists of a few fixed-ended questions on which the student rates the teacher.

The scores on these fixed-ended questions are then used to generate a statistical report. Regularly these fixed ended questions are supplemented with some open-ended questions. There are several reasons to include open-ended questions in a SET questionnaire. Open-ended questions allow a greater freedom of expression and are less influenced by the research as students don't have to fit their answer in standard answer categories (Foddy, 1994). Although open-ended questions allow for a greater range of expression and valuable information might get lost in answers to fixed-ended questions, little research has focused upon the answers given to these questions (Alhija & Fresko, 2009).

In SET, the comments of students reflect the complexity of teaching environments and the way each student reacts to specific environments or teaching strategies (Lewis 2001). In that perspective - as different authors (Alhija & Fresko, 2009; Hodges & Stanton, 2007; Smith Welicker- Pollak, 2008) pointed out - comments can yield more and more useful information on important educational issues and provide better insights to improve them. For instance, student comments are more specific than a statistical report and can contain actual ideas to improve teaching (Hammond, Taylor, & McMenamin, 2003). An analysis of students' comments can provide useful insight into aspects of teaching and courses that students find important and verify whether these aspects are different from the ones that are generally measured in SET-instruments (Symmons, 2006). Furthermore, students' comments in SET are important for teachers. Some studies indicate that instructors prefer written comments (as opposed to feedback based on statistical data) (Centra, 1973; Lewis and Svinicki, 2001). The answers to these questions have greater potential to influence them than statistical reports (Alhija & Fresko, 2009).

It is given that in every job, challenges as a newbie are considered a normal thing. However, when there is no action being taken between the employer and the employee, growth to both sides will not happen. Employers have the responsibility to support their employees in coping with professional challenges. This not only ensures a productive and motivated workforce but also fosters a positive work environment. Specifically, the employer must provide a safe and healthy working environment such as free hazards workplace, implementing a work – life balance adhering labor and civil services laws to prevent employees from burning out. Another is to provide professional development opportunities such as providing trainings, workshops, skills development programs.

Employers can also offer mentoring opportunities to their learning through tuition assistance or certifications.

According to Ishikawa Kaoru (1986), the fishbone diagram is a visual way to look at cause and effect. It is a more structured approach than some other tools available for brainstorming the grounds of a problem. The problem or result is exposed to the head or mouth of the fish. Possible contributing causes remain listed on the smaller "bones" under various cause categories. A fishbone diagram can help identify potential causes for a problem that might not otherwise be considered by directing the team to consider the types and think of alternative reasons. Include team members who have personal knowledge of the processes and systems involved in the problem or event being investigated. To sum it all, fishbone diagrams are simplified visualizations used to identify and illustrate the causes of a specific event. Understanding the challenges of the new faculty members in Tarlac State University in teaching can help the institution develop actions that address the issues. A cause-and-effect diagram, often called a "fishbone" diagram, can help in brainstorming to identify possible causes of a problem and sort ideas into functional categories (Mary Walton, 1992).

Research Questions

The study sought to answer the following:

1. Is there any significant relationship between the challenges encountered by the novice faculty members to their profiles in terms of:
 - 1.1 number of years in teaching; and
 - 1.2 educational qualifications?
2. To what extent do the teachers encounter challenges in the instruction process in the following areas:
 - 2.1 daily lesson preparations; and
 - 2.2 instructional management?
3. What is the performance of the novice faculty members in terms of their Students' Evaluation in Teaching (SET)?
4. Is there any significant relationship between the challenges encountered by the novice faculty members to their performance in SET?
5. Based on the identified challenges, what proposed training plan can be given to faculty members to address these challenges?

METHODOLOGY

The study pursued the cooperation of the new faculty members from the nine (9) colleges, namely: College of Arts and Social Sciences, College of Teacher Education, College of Architecture and Fine Arts, College of Engineering and Technology, College of Computer Studies, College of Science, College of Public Administration and Governance, College of Business Administration, and College of Criminal Justice Education in Tarlac State University. The study focused on the challenges experienced

by the novice faculty members in terms of their instructional task along with their Students' Teaching Evaluation during the school year 2020 – 2022, which became a basis for the proposed training plan as an intervention.

The study was limited only to the faculty members hired during the academic year 2020 – 2021 regardless of their job status. The participation of the identified faculty members significantly helped the institution to implement the action plan to help the novice faculty members improve their instructional strategies and cope with their instructional challenges. With the help of the TSU – HRDMO in providing the data of the newly – hired faculty members, the researchers were able to identify the Student Evaluation of Teaching (SET) given by the students together with the instructional rating of the new faculty members in their Individual Performance Commitment and Review (IPCR). The table shows the number of news faculty members hired in different colleges during the Academic Year 2020 – 2022. The CAFA has outnumbered other colleges in terms of news faculty members that were rated using SET and IPCR.

Table 1 Percentage of New Faculty Members in Every Colleges

<u>Colleges</u>	<u>Percent</u>
<u>College of Science (COS)</u>	<u>20.6</u>
<u>College of Architecture and Fine Arts (CAFA)</u>	<u>29.4</u>
<u>College of Business Administration (CPAG)</u>	<u>14.7</u>
<u>College of Arts and Social Sciences (CASS)</u>	<u>5.9</u>
<u>College of Engineering and Technology (CET)</u>	<u>8.8</u>
<u>College of Teacher Education</u>	<u>2.9</u>
<u>College of Computing Studies</u>	<u>8.8</u>
<u>College of Criminal Justice Education</u>	<u>2.9</u>
<u>College of Public Administration and Governance</u>	<u>5.9</u>
<u>Total</u>	<u>100.0</u>

To identify the challenges experience by the new faculty members in terms of their class preparations, class management and instruction, the research developed and validated a 5 – Likert Scale survey questionnaire that consist of a self-evaluation category (developing, proficiency accomplished, and distinguished), that were mutually exclusive categories which may ask both single answers. Validation is an important process to ensure that the developed instrument can measure what it intends to measure. Validity also refers to the ability to predict specific events, or its relationship to measure other constructs based on the way a scale was constructed (DeVellis, 2017).

The study used a root cause analysis, specifically a fishbone diagram that involves the challenges experienced by the new faculty members and became the basis of an intervention program. The study will focus on the new faculty members of different colleges hired during the Academic Year 2020 – 2021. The root cause analysis and the faculty evaluation results became the basis of intervention or program activities which can help the new faculty members cope with their identified challenges and improve their efficacy in instruction. A total population sampling was used in collecting the data needed in the study. Total population sampling is a type of purposive sampling wherein the whole population of interest is studied. To understand the challenges and coping strategies of the novice faculty members, the study used thematic analysis. Thematic analysis is a widely used but then frequently misunderstood technique for analyzing qualitative data. It was a practical and approachable instrument for qualitative researchers, but ambiguity surrounding the method's conceptual foundations and imprecision in its description have made its usage and acceptability among researchers difficult.

In terms of the data analysis the study used a Multiple Regression analysis to identify the relationship between the profiles of the faculty members specifically their educational attainment and teaching experience to the challenges they experience as a novice faculty member. A multiple regression is an extension of simple linear regression. It is used when we want to predict the value of a variable based on the value of two or more other variables. The variable we want to predict is called the dependent variable (or sometimes, the outcome, target or criterion variable). The variables we are using to predict the value of the dependent variable are called the independent variables (or sometimes, the predictor, explanatory or regressor variables).

Alongside Multiple Regression Analysis, the study also used a Paired sample T-test to identify if there was any significant relationship between the three (3) challenges to their Student Evaluation in Teaching (SET). The paired sample t-test, sometimes called the dependent sample t-test, is a statistical procedure used to determine whether the mean difference between two sets of observations is zero. In a paired sample t-test, each subject or entity is measured twice, resulting in pairs of observations. Common applications of the paired sample t-test include case-control studies or repeated-measures designs. Suppose you are interested in evaluating the effectiveness of a company training program.

RESULTS

The study sought to determine the challenges experienced by the novice faculty members in teaching. The study also assessed the relationship of the faculty members' profiles specifically their educational attainment and teaching experience to their identified challenges. Along with this, the study also evaluated the effect of these challenges with the faculty members' Student Evaluation in Teaching (SET) rating. These observations confirmed and extended previous studies (e.g. De Wever, B., Vanderlinde R., Tuytensm M. and Aelterman, A. 2016; Achinstein, B., & Barret, A. 2004; Britt, P.M. 1997) which states that faculty members have different challenges experienced and techniques to coped with.

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE CHALLENGES EXPERIENCE BY THE NOVICE FACULTY MEMBERS TO THEIR PROFILES IN EDUCATION ATTAINMENT AND TEACHING EXPERIENCE

The study disclosed that in terms of their teaching experience, majority of the faculty members in TSU have been in the teaching profession for less than a year (35%). The data also revealed that most of them are master's degree holder already. Along with this, the participants also revealed that most of them (55%) are handling more than 18 units of teaching loads in different subjects. Being a faculty member in the higher education is crucial specially the alignment of programs being taught and the educational attainment or the field of specialization of the faculty members. In this study, the data revealed that there were still few faculty members (40%) who are not aligned to the programs they handled which somehow became one of their challenges in terms of class preparation, class management and instruction. Aside from this, the data also revealed that most of the faculty members were on Temporary Status and do not have tenure status (75%) and only few (35%) have been in the teaching profession for at least seven years.

The study used a Multiple Regression Analysis to identify the substantial association between the instructional challenges of novice faculty members to their profiles specifically their teaching experience and educational attainment. Multiple regression analysis is used to predict the value of a variable based on the value of group variables. The following table shows the multiple regression analysis used in the study.

Educational Attainment to Challenges

Table 2. R and R-squared values

Model Summary^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.421 ^a	.177	.023	.556	1.075

a. Predictors: (Constant), Highest Education Attainment

Table 3. F- Ration in the Analysis of Variances

ANOVA^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	38.087	5	102.362	32.243	.001 ^b
	Residual	98.191	19	25.512		
	Total	126.278	24			

a. Predictors: (Constant): Highest Education Attainment

Table 4. Unstandardized Coefficients

Coefficients^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.949	.469		4.156	.001
	Class Preparation	-.295	.211	-.433	-1.394	.002
	Class Environment	-.120	.366	-.162	-.328	.007
	Instruction	.443	.331	.652	1.341	.019

a Predictors (Constant): Highest Education Attainment

Based on the result of multiple regression presented above and was used to predict the effect of Educational Attainment of faculty members to their challenges in Class Preparation, Class Environment, and Instruction. These variables are statistically significant with the predicted $F(5,19) = 32.243$, $p < 0.0005$. The challenges in Class Preparation and Class Environment showed statistically significantly affected by the educational attainment of faculty members except their challenges in Instruction. This implies that the challenges of faculty members in giving instruction does not affect their educational background and years in the teaching profession.

Teaching Experience to Challenges

Table 5. R and R-squared

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.544 ^a	.296	.164	2.34775	1.419
a. Predictors (Constant): Teaching Experience					

Table 6. F – ratio in Analysis of Variance

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	37.087	5	102.362	32.393	.001 ^b
	Residual	88.191	16	25.512		
	Total	125.278	21			
a. Predictors: (Constant): Teaching Experience						

Table 7. Unstandardized Coefficients

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	15.675	1.981		2.864	.001
	Class Preparation	-1.725	.893	-.555	-1.932	.001
	Class Environment	-0.408	1.545	-.416	-.912	.000
	Instruction	0.650	1.397	.532	1.181	.005
a. Predictors: (Constant): Years in Teaching						

Based on the result of the multiple regression presented above and was run to predict the of Teaching Experience with their identified challenges in Class Preparation, Class Environment, and Instruction. These variables statistically significant with the predicted $F(5,16) = 32.393$, $p < 0.0005$. All three identified challenges showed statistically significantly affected by the teaching experiences of faculty members.

The CHALLENGES ENCOUNTERED in INSTRUCTION of the NOVICE FACULTY MEMBERS and THE WAY THEY COPE WITH IT

Challenges were categorized into personal and professional challenges, which may benefit the study in seeking further understanding among novice faculty members of the University.

Personal Challenges

Based on the responses of the participants, there were various responses in defining their biggest challenge in the University. Two of the participants emphasized that their struggles to secure a tenured position as stated, "My biggest challenge during my more than ten years of employment as a lecturer in TSU is not being able to secure a permanent position because my undergraduate course was not vertically aligned. This also gave difficulty to understand the assigned courses for me to teach." This can also be like the study of Clandinin, D. J., et. Al (2015) about beginning teachers, it showed that one of the themes highlighted was about tensions around contracts, as it focuses on the likelihood of getting jobs.

Aside from the security of tenure, additional tasks given to the teachers, like additional responsibilities on providing research and participating in extension programs have also been identified which highly affects their preparations during class and still manages to be an effective teacher despite of the lingering thoughts of a secured position. Meanwhile, another participant indicated that diversity of students based on their Senior High School strands as his initial struggles in the University which also affects his effectiveness in teaching, as explained "Most students do not have the knowledge when it comes to basic topics, so I must adjust for them so the students with the knowledge will have to "repeat" the topics again. It is like the "advanced" students need to slow down in learning so their classmates can catch up."

Since most of the participants were hired during the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic, they also find teaching in a virtual set-up to be also challenging, as verified in one participant's response that, "Virtual teaching for me is challenging since I'm not used to it and it lacks live interaction which is one of the most important part of an active learning and it decreases the sincerity of your personal advices to your student". Lack of the usual teacher-student interaction during the online learning continues to be the biggest concerns in education (Selvaraj, A., et.al,2021). Students have dealt various difficulties that can also affect their learning in the online set-up as technology is named as one of the barriers in this pandemic era (Baticulon, R.E., Sy, J.J., Alberto, N.R.I. et al., 2021). This is also the same case when it comes to the educators. In the study of Dayagbil, F.T., Palompon, D.R., et. al. (2021), they conducted a survey to both students and faculty members. One of its themes showed that even teachers concluded that the traditional way of teaching is no longer effective in the online learning set-up and adjustments to teaching were implemented. About 90% of educators concluded enthusiasm for online classes, but in truth, most are not yet ready for a full and immediate virtual learning set -

up, especially when one is unfamiliar on using technology in class (Sahito Z, Shah SS and Pelser A-M, 2022).

A similar story was also highlighted by one of the participants and narrated her worries on the future quality of education online, “I think the biggest challenge I have faced during my employment (until now) is on how I am going to share and transfer the lessons and learnings in this pandemic where everyone is not entitled for the online learning setup. Next is the reality that almost all my students are very dependent on their classmates and with online calculator.”

Wide variety of coping up strategies were indicated, ranging from both intrapersonal and interpersonal capabilities. Responses from some of the participants would deal with the certain challenges by enhancing themselves and in most participants’ terms, the ability to be flexible and “find ways to make our discussion more fun and enjoyable” can get them through their struggles. As one of the characteristics of a teacher, adjustments for the students were also made to make sure that they can understand the lessons making patience and an important virtue in teaching, as experienced by one participant, stating that “most students do not have the knowledge when it comes to basic topics so I have to adjust for them so the students with the knowledge will have to “repeat” the topics again. It is like the “advanced” students need to slow down in learning so their classmates can catch up”. Statements referring to spiritual ways or “faith” was also mentioned in their responses.

On the other hand, their students also served as part of their inspiration in overcoming their challenges, as narrated “I still do my best to be an effective instructor to my students. In all honesty, my students inspire to teach passionately even though I cannot secure an item in TSU. They inspire me because of the positive comments I get from them every end of the semester.” And “both problems I have mentioned made me serve as an alarm clock that woke and reminded them not to cheat and not to make their own ghosts of their future.”. The idea that students can be able to easily understand topics despite the current struggles and difficulties in information and communication technology (ICT) was also one of the special joys of one participant, recounting that “It makes me happy and proud when my students say that I am good in teaching math because I make it easier for them to understand”. Studies show that being grateful were portrayed by teachers as their way to maintain composure and good mental health during the pandemic (Hidalgo-Andrade P, Hermosa-Bosano C, Paz C., 2021).

Professional Challenges

Results of the participants on the implementation of professional development mainly focuses on two categories: enhancement of skills and knowledge in the virtual platform and assurance on good mental health by developing other related skills. Concerns on being familiar with the recent technologies, like “being able to familiarize oneself over new materials and applications in teaching, especially mathematics”, as stated by one participant. Another participant narrated his take on the virtual mode of instruction, “Virtual teaching for me is challenging since I’m not used to it and it lacks live

interaction which is one of the most important parts of an active learning". According to the literature review of Leary, H., Dopp, C., Turley, C., et.al (2020), various themes were explored but professional development programs is the most highlighted theme as it also suggests that universities must also consider this as the major area for improvement. Furthermore, aside from virtual teaching, one participant also mentioned time management skills as the focus for professional development. Time management was known as one of the primary skills in learning, not only as a student but also as a teacher.

All responses of the participants see professional development skills, ideas, and strategies as essential in teaching virtually. According to one participant, this helps him cope up more on his challenges in the field, describing that "It allowed me to discuss and present properly virtually and helped students struggling to find a way to join the class discussions". Moreover, professional development like enriching oneself on latest ways to teach online pursues more assurance on the side of the novice faculty member, as defined "There were webinars I attended on how to teach virtually the subjects that were difficult to teach like math and computer.

These webinars helped me strategized my teaching methods to be effective to my students. It was a great help on my part because I learned to adapt to the challenges of virtual type of instruction"

Majority of them also mentioned that the implementation of various ways for the online set-up could also eventually help their respective colleges in teaching different subjects, "I think it can be of great help also to my college because I can be able to make/create a syllabus for virtual type of instruction to the subjects" and "I think the familiarity of the applications will help my college. For example, the equations needed in the discussion can be written in an app called latex, so it will be easy to teach students the equations needed. The whiteboard online also helped to present the topics clearly". Meanwhile, learning how to teach virtually was also seen as the only way to cope up. One participant shared his experience that "because obviously we are in the middle of a pandemic right now so the only way to cope up with the quality of the face-to-face class is to be knowledgeable in this virtual world."

Nonetheless, it can also be seen as other challenges as narrated by another participant in order "for faculty members to be able to give their best and also take care of their mental health, prevent from burnout". As teaching is one of the most arduous professions, burnout can be common as defined as "which can manifest itself psychologically, emotionally, and physically. While stress and its effects are unavoidable, these pressures can be mitigated if appropriate action is taken" (Hurley, 2021 p. 22, as cited in Miller, M. L., 2022).

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE CHALLENGES OF NOVICE FACULTY MEMBERS TO THEIR STUDENT EVALUATION IN TEACHING (SET)

The study used a paired sample t-test to individually understand the relationship of each instructional challenges of the faculty members to their Midterm and Final Student Evaluation in Teaching (SET).

There are three tables presented below in each paired variables such as the Paired Samples Statistics, Paired Samples Correlations, and Paired Samples Test. Paired Samples Statistics provides univariate descriptive statistics (mean, sample size, standard deviation, and standard error) for each variable entered. Paired Samples Correlations shows the bivariate Pearson correlation coefficient (with a two-tailed test of significance) for each pair of variables entered. Paired Samples Test gives the hypothesis test results.

Challenges in Class Preparation to SET Ratings

Table 8. Paired Samples Statistics

Paired Samples Statistics					
		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	Rating on the First Sem	4.1715	20	.52522	.11744
	Class Preparation	2.55	20	.826	.185
Pair 2	Rating on the Second Sem	4.2500	20	.48746	.10900
	Class Preparation	2.55	20	.826	.185

Table 9. Paired Samples Correlations

Paired Samples Correlations				
		N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair 1	Rating on the First Sem & Class Preparation	20	.762	.001
Pair 2	Rating on the Second Sem & Class Preparation	20	.973	.000

Table 10. Paired Samples Test

Paired Samples Test							
		Paired Differences					Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		
					Lower	Upper	
Pair 1	Rating on the First Sem - Class Preparation	1.62150	1.01006	.22586	1.14878	2.09422	.001
Pair 2	Rating on the Second Sem - Class Preparation	1.70000	9.6204	.21512	1.24975	2.15025	.001

Based on the paired sample t – test presented on the table above, the SET ratings for the first and second semester were positively correlated at (($r = .762, .973$), $p < 0.005, 0.001$). On average, the second semester SET rating were 1.70 points higher than the first semester SET ratings (96% CI [1.24, 2.15]). Thus, the challenges experienced by the novice faculty members during their class preparations show a significant effect to their SET ratings.

Challenges in Class Management to SET Ratings

Table 11. Paired Samples Statistics

Paired Samples Statistics					
		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	Class Management	2.55	20	.759	.170
	Rating on the First Sem	4.1715	20	.52522	.11744
Pair 2	Class Management	2.55	20	.759	.170
	Rating on the Second Sem	4.2500	20	.48746	.10900

Table 12. Paired Samples Correlations

Paired Samples Correlations				
		N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair 1	Class Management & Rating on the First Sem	20	-.124	.004
Pair 2	Class Management & Rating on the Second Sem	20	-.061	.002

Table 13. Paired Samples Test

Paired Samples Test							
		Paired Differences					Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		
					Lower	Upper	
Pair 1	Class Management - Rating on the First Sem	-1.62150	.97506	.21803	-2.07784	-1.16516	.005
Pair 2	Class Management - Rating on the Second Sem	-1.70000	.92693	.20727	-2.13382	-1.26618	.005

Based on the table presented above for the paired sample t – test result, the SET ratings for the first and second semester partially negatively correlated at (($r = -.124, .604$,

p<0.005, 0.005). On average, the first semester SET rating was - 1.62 points higher than the second semester SET ratings (97% CI [-2.07, -1.26]. Thus, the challenges experienced by the novice faculty members in terms of class management showed a significant effect on their SET ratings.

Challenges in Instruction to SET Ratings

Table 14. Paired Samples Statistics

Paired Samples Statistics					
		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	Instruction	2.50	20	.827	.185
	Rating on the First Sem	4.1715	20	.52522	.11744
Pair 2	Instruction	2.50	20	.827	.185
	Rating on the Second Sem	4.2500	20	.48746	.10900

Table 15. Paired Samples Correlations

Paired Samples Correlations				
		N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair 1	Instruction & Rating on the First Sem	20	.009	.970
Pair 2	Instruction & Rating on the Second Sem	20	.031	.896

Table 16. Paired Samples Test

Paired Samples Test							
		Paired Differences					Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		
					Lower	Upper	
Pair 1	Instruction - Rating on the First Sem	1.67150	.93385	.22000	2.13196	1.21104	.000
Pair 2	Instruction - Rating on the Second Sem	1.75000	.94687	.21173	2.19315	1.30685	.000

Based on the presented table above for the paired sample t – test result, the SET ratings for the first and second semester significantly positively correlated at ((r = .009, .031, p<0.001, 0.000). On average, the second semester SET rating were 1.75 points higher than the first semester SET ratings (94% CI [2.19, 1.30]. Thus, the challenges experience by the novice faculty members in their instruction shows a significantly affect their SET ratings.

PROPOSED INTERVENTION PLAN TO HELP THE NOVICE FACULTY MEMBERS IN THEIR SET PERFORMANCE RATINGS

While there is no such thing as a teacher evaluation tool that is 100% flawless, based on the responses gathered from the novice faculty members on the University, novice faculty members can utilize evaluation feedback to improve their instruction and student learning in their classes.

Collaborating with a colleague is among the best ways to think critically about your teaching methods. A good sounding board is a coworker who can clarify feedback and aid in comprehending the evaluation's recommendations. The best technique to satisfy the needs of students in the classroom should always be discussed, therefore a new faculty member should always seek out a dependable colleague. It may be difficult to receive feedback that cannot be evaluated in nature, nevertheless, think about inviting dependable coworkers to be in your class. This cooperative effort can be carried out in a risk-free setting and may also serve as proof that the new instructor is committed to personal development.

Our university was founded on the belief that problems may be overcome by combining the power of discovery with creative thinking and analytical thinking, including problems that arise throughout the educational process. Although researching successful teaching techniques in the field of teaching and learning is a smart way to do so, self – reflection in teaching is the most crucial component of a great teaching practice. According to John Dewey, an American philosopher and educational reformer, believed that reflection was an essential component of learning. Dewey defined reflection as "a methodical, rigorous, disciplined way of thinking" that contributed to intellectual development, as noted by Dewey researcher Carol Rodgers.

It is beneficial to get feedback from your students on their experiences as learners in your class while evaluating your instruction. There are several techniques to obtain student feedback from anonymous surveys, open-ended feedback form and class polls, whatever is appropriate to your assessment objectives in teaching.

With these intervention techniques, the administration of the University can come up with a program that may help the faculty members to improve their teaching such as conducting In-Service Training focusing on class preparation and management. Conduct a mentoring session in every department of the colleges for proper guidance from the novice faculty members which may help them answer the questions as they have in mind, giving them a difficult time in their journey in the teaching profession. From these findings, one of the colleges considered the results to be disseminated, especially that the study was about the faculty members of all colleges in Tarlac State University. The College of Science held the "COS RISE" seminar, which all full-time faculty members were required to attend. The objective of the seminar conducted is to address highlighted areas in instruction such as crafting a syllabus and identifying appropriate teaching methods to type of instruction and students, different assessment methods, differentiating traditional to modern teaching methods and technological advancements in teaching. With this, the

faculty members were enlightened about techniques and methods that can be used to improve their teaching and to increase the evaluation of students in their class.

DISCUSSION

The aim of the study was to determine the challenges of novice faculty members in teaching. The findings of the study reveal that the profiles of the faculty members specifically their educational attainment and teaching experience have a strong relationship to the three (3) identified challenges such as class preparation, class management, and instruction. To elaborate further, the education attainment of faculty members has a strong relationship only to their challenges in class preparation and class management whereas the teaching experience showed strong relationship to the three identified challenges in teaching.

To support the claims of the current study, the thematic analysis being conducted to gather the insights from the faculty members showed that faculty members also experience other challenges aside from their class preparation, management and instruction which was categorized into two: personal and professional challenges. The personal challenges highlighted the themes about tensions around contracts, as they focus on the likelihood of getting jobs. Aside from the security of tenure, additional tasks given to the teachers, like additional responsibilities on providing research and participating in extension programs have also been identified which highly affects their preparations during class and still manages to be an effective teacher despite of the lingering thoughts of a secured position. On the other hand, the professional challenges also revealed that most faculty members showed problems in their enhancement of skills and knowledge in the virtual platform and assurance on good mental health by developing other related skills. Aside from virtual teaching, one participant also mentioned time management skills as the focus for professional development. Time management was known as one of the primary skills in learning, not only as a student but also as a teacher.

Despite the challenges experienced by the novice faculty members, none of them showed weakness and managed to deal with these challenges. Wide variety of coping up strategies were indicated, ranging from both intrapersonal and interpersonal capabilities. Responses from some of the participants would deal with the certain challenges by enhancing themselves and in most participants' terms, the ability to be flexible and "find ways to make our discussion more fun and enjoyable" can get them through their struggles. Majority of them also mentioned that the implementation of various ways for the online set-up could also eventually help their respective colleges in teaching different subjects and attending different webinars and workshops helped them a lot.

The study also revealed that the Ratings of the faculty members in their Student Evaluation in Teaching (SET) was greatly affected by the three identified challenges. From these three challenges, the study showed that instruction strongly affected the ratings of the faculty members among the three. Over the last decade, there has been a dramatic increase in the use of student ratings, and this may serve to aide administrative

evaluations for teacher effectiveness and make it as a basis for making decisions concerning the improvement of faculty member's instruction, promotions and permanency. Efforts to improve instruction may be classified into two: instructor development and within – class improvement which was both showed by the current findings of the study.

Conclusions

The study focused on identifying causes that somehow gave novice faculty members difficulty in teaching leading them to acquire a Satisfactory to below satisfactory during their Student Evaluation in Teaching (SET) that were done at the end of every semester. From the data collected and analyzed, the researchers concluded that most of the faculty members who were novice are at the College of Architecture and Fine Arts followed by the College of Science. Upon using interview as the data gathering method, which revealed that class preparation, class management, classroom environment, and instructional methods were the most aspects of teaching to which the faculty finds quite difficult, they still find ways to cope with these problems. Despite these challenges, none of the faculty members showed their weaknesses and still try to do ways to improve themselves. Aside from instructional challenges, the faculty members also admitted that they were experiencing problems with how they can improve themselves personally and professionally, especially that the support given to them by the administration was not enough and learning by themselves from the lack of support or assistance from experts was difficult.

Upon the discussion in the SET results, the study also revealed that most of the faculty members who have given a Satisfactory and below rating were novice faculty members which led the researchers to push through this study. Some variables were also considered as factors to these problems experienced by faculty members such as unaligned educational qualifications and lack of teaching experience that showed a relevant relationship to their personal and professional growth as part of the academe.

From these results, only one of the colleges opt to take action after receiving the results of the study. The College of Science, known as one of the colleges with newly – hired faculty members conducted a seminar workshop entitled, “College of Science – Research, Instruction, Skilling and Extension” which have an objective to equipped faculty members other skills and techniques not only in teaching but also in other aspects needed by a faculty member in a higher academe. Invited experts from the field of instruction highlighted different new methods and techniques in teaching, handling students, and strategies in assessing students' ability. Technological advancement was also introduced so that the faculty members can technology not only teaching but also providing a productive and exciting classroom environment for their students.

Recommendations

Future researchers might consider exploring other SUCs and identify problems that are common to their faculty members regardless of their employment status. This might help the colleges or institutions to identify future activities that might help the faculty members improve their instruction.

To SUCs and other schools who considered the SET as one of the standards of re-considering the employment status of the faculty members and require SETs as one of the needed criteria of their tenure and performance evaluations, SUCs might consider providing guidelines to what measures or SETs percentage will be included in their performance evaluation. These recommendations will help the faculty members to be firm with their stand as a faculty member avoiding the tendencies of being intimidated on their students since they hold a big deal on their employment.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors declare that they have complied with all ethical standards applicable to this research. No studies with human participants or animals were conducted by the authors.

Acknowledgments

The authors are immeasurably grateful to Tarlac State University for giving me this opportunity to conduct this study. Many thanks to the participants who shared their precious time and effort to provide the pertinent data. To our HRDMO staff who patiently accommodated us throughout the conduct of the study.

The authors are so thankful to all evaluators whose constructive comments and insightful suggestions helped improve this paper.

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